

ImproRisk

“Exposure Assessment of Cypermethrin”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Cypermethrin is a synthetic pyrethroid used as an insecticide in large-scale commercial agricultural applications as well as in consumer products for domestic purposes. It behaves as a fast-acting neurotoxin in insects. Cypermethrin is moderately toxic through skin contact or ingestion. Pyrethroids may adversely affect the central nervous system.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the chronic dietary Cypermethrin intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 5 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary Cypermethrin exposure.

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.204 and 0.512 µg/kg b.w. per week (Table 4.2). It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 5 µg/Kg b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers due to their lower body weight, but also much lower than the ADI. There was no significant difference in Cypermethrin intake between genders and different geographical areas.

In general fruits and some vegetables were the main contributors to the total Cypermethrin exposure. Apples (11.7%), grapes (9.0%), tomatoes (7.5%), potatoes (5.6%), peaches (5.5%) and cucumbers (4.0%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Cypermethrin intake.

2 Introduction

Cypermethrin is a synthetic pyrethroid used as an insecticide in large-scale commercial agricultural applications as well as in consumer products for domestic purposes. It behaves as a fast-acting neurotoxin in insects. It is easily degraded on soil and plants but can be effective for weeks when applied to indoor inert surfaces. Exposure to sunlight, water and oxygen will accelerate its decomposition. Cypermethrin is highly toxic to fish, bees and aquatic insects. It is also found in many household ant and cockroach killers.

Cypermethrin is moderately toxic through skin contact or ingestion. It may cause irritation to the skin and eyes. Symptoms of dermal exposure include numbness, tingling, itching, burning sensation, loss of bladder control, incoordination, seizures and possible death. Pyrethroids may adversely affect the central nervous system.

It may cause allergic skin reactions in humans. Excessive exposure can cause nausea, headache, muscle weakness, salivation, shortness of breath and seizures. In humans, cypermethrin is deactivated by enzymatic hydrolysis to several carboxylic acid metabolites, which are eliminated in the urine. Worker exposure to the chemical can be monitored by measurement of the urinary metabolites, while severe overdosage may be confirmed by quantitation of cypermethrin in blood or plasma.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the chronic dietary Cypermethrin intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 5 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary Cypermethrin exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Cypermethrin occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2014-2020, and are shown in Tables 3.1. Only plant origin food was selected to be used in the calculation of the exposure. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOQ were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOQ for the Middle-bound scenario and LOQ for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors

were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee and cocoa beverages, tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. The aggregated occurrence dataset is: Cypermethrin 2014-2020_Aggregated_Plant origin_Final.xlsx with occurrence estimates for 259 food items.

Table 3.1 shows the aggregated occurrence values used in the exposure assessment of Cypermethrin

Table 3.1: Aggregated occurrence values for Cypermethrin

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03GG	Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	1	20		0.0290	0.0715	0.1140
A03GH	Ingredients for coffee, cocoa, tea, and herbal infusions	2	20		0.0290	0.0715	0.1140
A03HQ	Tea leaves derivatives and tea ingredients	3	20		0.0290	0.0715	0.1140
A04KK	Teas leaves, dry and/or fermented, and similar	4	20		0.0290	0.0715	0.1140
A011X	Legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	1	152		0.0031	0.0195	0.0358
A016S	Spices	2	14		0.0250	0.0504	0.0757
A01AY	Processed legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	2	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A04RG	Legumes	2	129		0.0009	0.0146	0.0282
A04RH	Nuts, oilseeds and oilfruits	2	8		0.0000	0.0438	0.0875
A011Y	Legumes fresh seeds (beans, peas etc.)	3	27		0.0000	0.0102	0.0204
A012R	Pulses (dried legume seeds)	3	102		0.0012	0.0157	0.0303
A014C	Tree nuts	3	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A015F	Oilseeds	3	7		0.0000	0.0464	0.0929
A017X	Seed spices	3	4		0.0000	0.0312	0.0625
A019Z	Root and rhizome spices	3	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01AK	Bud spices	3	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A01AZ	Canned or jarred legumes	3	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A011Z	Beans (fresh seeds without pods) and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A012G	Peas (without pods) and similar-	4	23		0.0000	0.0076	0.0152
A012S	Beans (dry) and similar-	4	68		0.0006	0.0141	0.0276
A01BC	Canned or jarred peas	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0CGQ	Coriander seeds and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0500	0.1000
A0CGX	Ginger roots and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CHA	Capers buds and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0CZF	Anise seed and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DBP	Sunflower seeds and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DBQ	Sesame seeds and similar-	4	6		0.0000	0.0500	0.1000
A0DCD	Peas (dry) and similar-	4	15		0.0053	0.0209	0.0366
A0DCE	Lentils (dry) and similar-	4	19		0.0000	0.0174	0.0347
A0DYJ	Chestnuts and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A012A	Broad beans (without pods)	5	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A012J	Garden peas (without pods)	5	23		0.0000	0.0076	0.0152
A013H	Broad beans (dry)	5	7		0.0000	0.0143	0.0286
A013J	Garden peas (dry)	5	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A013M	Chickpeas (dry)	5	13		0.0061	0.0218	0.0376
A013N	Black eyed peas (dry)	5	16		0.0025	0.0169	0.0312
A013Q	Lentils (dry)	5	19		0.0000	0.0174	0.0347
A014J	Chestnuts	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A015K	Sesame seeds	5	6		0.0000	0.0500	0.1000
A015L	Sunflower seeds	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A017Y	Anise seed	5	3		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A018D	Coriander seed	5	1		0.0000	0.0500	0.1000
A01AB	Ginger roots	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AM	Capers buds	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A000J	Grains and grain-based products	1	207		0.0017	0.0167	0.0317
A000K	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	2	197		0.0018	0.0171	0.0323
A00CV	Breakfast cereals	2	10		0.0000	0.0095	0.0190
A000L	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	3	147		0.0022	0.0174	0.0326
A04KS	Cereal and cereal-like flours	3	45		0.0009	0.0166	0.0322
A04LK	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	3	10		0.0000	0.0095	0.0190
A0BY1	Groats	3	5		0.0000	0.0120	0.0240
A000F	Oat and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A000S	Maize and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0200	0.0400
A000Y	Common millet and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0183	0.0367
A001C	Rice and similar-	4	114		0.0019	0.0184	0.0349
A001M	Wheat and similar-	4	19		0.0056	0.0112	0.0167
A002G	Buckwheat flour	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002L	Barley flour	4	11		0.0037	0.0124	0.0210
A002Y	Oat flour	4	5		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A002Z	Oat groats	4	3		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A003J	Rye flour	4	7		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A003X	Wheat flour	4	21		0.0000	0.0231	0.0462
A004G	Bulgur	4	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A04KH	Buckwheat and other pseudo-cereals and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0183	0.0367
A04QY	Cereal flakes and similar	4	10		0.0000	0.0095	0.0190
A0D9Y	Barley and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A000A	Teff grain	5	3		0.0000	0.0183	0.0367
A000N	Buckwheat	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000P	Barley grains	5	3		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A000R	Quinoa grain	5	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A001D	Rice grain	5	114		0.0019	0.0184	0.0349
A003M	Rye flour, wholemeal	5	7		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A004C	Wheat flour, durum	5	5		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A00DN	Processed oat-based flakes	5	6		0.0000	0.0092	0.0183
A00DY	Processed rye-based flakes	5	4		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A001E	Rice grain, brown	6	11		0.0010	0.0224	0.0437
A00FJ	Vegetables and vegetable products	1	595		0.1097	0.1226	0.1355
A00FL	Flowering brassica	2	19		0.0089	0.0137	0.0184
A00GX	Bulb vegetables	2	28		0.0000	0.0079	0.0157
A00HN	Fruiting vegetables	2	255		0.0028	0.0156	0.0283
A00KR	Leafy vegetables	2	144		0.0490	0.0602	0.0714
A00PB	Legumes with pod	2	39		0.0327	0.0491	0.0655
A00QF	Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-)	2	59		0.0000	0.0148	0.0297

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A00RR	Stems/stalks eaten as vegetables	2	20		0.2744	0.2748	0.2751
A00VQ	Herbs and edible flowers	2	29		0.0410	0.0712	0.1013
A00ZA	Processed or preserved vegetables and similar	2	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A00FM	Broccoli and similar-	3	17		0.0100	0.0147	0.0194
A00FT	Head brassica	3	16		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A00HB	Onions and similar-	3	28		0.0000	0.0079	0.0157
A00HP	Solanacea	3	156		0.0043	0.0163	0.0284
A00JK	Cucurbits fruiting vegetables	3	99		0.0005	0.0143	0.0282
A00KS	Lettuces and salad plants	3	51		0.0183	0.0286	0.0390
A00MG	Spinach-type leaves	3	50		0.1221	0.1352	0.1483
A00PC	Beans (with pods) and similar-	3	39		0.0327	0.0491	0.0655
A04MA	Aromatic herbs	3	29		0.0410	0.0712	0.1013
A04MB	Processed tomato products	3	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A0DEN	Globe artichokes and similar-	3	6		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DEQ	Celeries and similar-	3	14		3.9205	3.9234	3.9262
A0DJQ	Grape leaves and similar species	3	27		0.0005	0.0127	0.0249
A0DLL	Cauliflowers and similar-	3	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DPB	Carrots and similar-	3	59		0.0000	0.0148	0.0297
A00FN	Broccoli	4	17		0.0100	0.0147	0.0194
A00FR	Cauliflowers	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00FX	Head cabbages and similar-	4	16		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A00HC	Onions	4	28		0.0000	0.0079	0.0157

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A00HQ	Tomatoes and similar-	4	76		0.0055	0.0175	0.0295
A00HZ	Peppers and similar-	4	50		0.0035	0.0167	0.0299
A00JC	Aubergines and similar-	4	23		0.0032	0.0123	0.0215
A00JL	Cucurbits with edible peel	4	71		0.0002	0.0135	0.0268
A00KD	Cucurbits with inedible peel	4	28		0.0010	0.0164	0.0318
A00LM	Roman rocket and similar-	4	9		0.0752	0.0947	0.1141
A00MH	Spinaches and similar-	4	46		0.1136	0.1271	0.1406
A00NB	Grape leaves	4	27		0.0005	0.0127	0.0249
A00PH	Broad beans (with pods)	4	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A00QH	Carrots	4	59		0.0000	0.0148	0.0297
A00RS	Globe artichokes	4	6		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00RY	Celeries	4	14		3.9205	3.9234	3.9262
A00ZE	Preserved concentrated tomatoes	4	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A04KD	Thyme and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DHZ	Parsley and similar-	4	10		0.0899	0.1029	0.1159
A0DJT	Chards and similar-	4	4		0.2200	0.2288	0.2375
A0DLB	Lettuces and similar-	4	42		0.0060	0.0145	0.0230
A0DMC	Okra and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0136	0.0271
A0ESV	Basils and mints	4	18		0.0161	0.0561	0.0961
A00FY	Head cabbages	5	16		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A00JA	Sweet peppers	5	50		0.0035	0.0167	0.0299
A00JD	Aubergines	5	23		0.0032	0.0123	0.0215
A00JF	Okra	5	7		0.0000	0.0136	0.0271
A00JH	Gojiberry	5	1		0.0000	0.0125	0.0250

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A00JQ	Courgettes and similar-	5	23		0.0000	0.0154	0.0309
A00KE	Melons and similar-	5	13		0.0017	0.0171	0.0325
A00KX	Lettuces (generic)	5	42		0.0060	0.0145	0.0230
A00MJ	Spinaches	5	46		0.1136	0.1271	0.1406
A00VV	Basil	5	5		0.0000	0.0090	0.0180
A00XV	Oregano	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A00XZ	Mints	5	13		0.0223	0.0742	0.1262
A00YE	Parsley	5	10		0.0899	0.1029	0.1159
A00ZF	Tomato paste	5	2		0.0000	0.0150	0.0300
A0DLQ	Watermelons and similar-	5	14		0.0005	0.0166	0.0326
A0DLV	Pumpkins and similar-	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DMB	Cucumbers and similar-	5	48		0.0003	0.0126	0.0249
A0DMX	Tomatoes	5	75		0.0056	0.0176	0.0296
A00HY	Cherry tomatoes	6	8		0.0324	0.0405	0.0486
A00JM	Cucumbers	6	48		0.0003	0.0126	0.0249
A00JR	Courgettes	6	23		0.0000	0.0154	0.0309
A00KF	Melons	6	13		0.0017	0.0171	0.0325
A00KH	Pumpkins	6	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00KJ	Watermelons	6	14		0.0005	0.0166	0.0326
A00ZR	Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	1	89		0.0000	0.0084	0.0167
A00ZS	Starchy roots and tubers	2	89		0.0000	0.0084	0.0167
A00ZY	Tropical root and tuber vegetables	3	7		0.0000	0.0107	0.0214
A0DPP	Potatoes and similar-	3	82		0.0000	0.0082	0.0163

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A00ZT	Potatoes	4	82		0.0000	0.0082	0.0163
A04JX	Cassava roots and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0107	0.0214
A010B	Taros	5	7		0.0000	0.0107	0.0214
A01BS	Fruit and fruit products	1	480		0.0516	0.0625	0.0733
A01ML	Processed fruit products	2	5		0.0000	0.0135	0.0270
A04RK	Fruit used as fruit	2	475		0.0521	0.0630	0.0738
A01BT	Citrus fruits	3	111		0.0177	0.0300	0.0422
A01DG	Pome fruits	3	83		0.0329	0.0419	0.0510
A01DT	Berries and small fruits	3	121		0.1134	0.1248	0.1362
A01GE	Stone fruits	3	58		0.0968	0.1074	0.1180
A01HE	Miscellaneous fruits with edible peel	3	30		0.0112	0.0293	0.0475
A01JS	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, small	3	15		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01LA	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	3	57		0.0069	0.0144	0.0220
A01MA	Dried fruit	3	5		0.0000	0.0135	0.0270
A01BX	Lemons and similar-	4	25		0.0004	0.0116	0.0228
A01CB	Mandarins and similar-	4	23		0.0132	0.0212	0.0293
A01CP	Oranges and similar-	4	62		0.0267	0.0407	0.0547
A01CX	Grapefruits and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A01DH	Apples and similar-	4	39		0.0407	0.0481	0.0556
A01DN	Pears and similar-	4	40		0.0274	0.0381	0.0489
A01DV	Grapes and similar fruits	4	57		0.2311	0.2371	0.2431
A01DZ	Strawberries and similar-	4	60		0.0092	0.0248	0.0403
A01ED	Cane fruits	4	3		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01GG	Cherries and similar-	4	14		0.1243	0.1443	0.1643
A01GL	Peaches and similar-	4	26		0.0923	0.0994	0.1065
A01GP	Plums and similar-	4	10		0.0063	0.0198	0.0333
A01HH	Table olives and similar-	4	23		0.0037	0.0250	0.0463
A01LN	Guavas and similar-	4	2		0.0995	0.0995	0.0995
A01MB	Dried prunes	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A01ME	Dried vine fruits (raisins etc.)	4	3		0.0000	0.0125	0.0250
A04JJ	Blueberries and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A04JS	Bananas and similar-	4	20		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DPV	Pineapples and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DQC	Granate apples and similar-	4	29		0.0067	0.0136	0.0204
A0DQF	Mangoes and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0200	0.0400
A0DRG	Kiwi fruits and similar-	4	15		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DRY	Figs and similar-	4	7		0.0356	0.0434	0.0513
A0DVX	Apricots and similar-	4	8		0.1765	0.1784	0.1802
A0DVY	Loquats and similar-	4	4		0.0120	0.0195	0.0270
A01BP	Table olives	5	23		0.0037	0.0250	0.0463
A01BY	Lemons	5	25		0.0004	0.0116	0.0228
A01CY	Grapefruits	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A01DJ	Apples	5	39		0.0407	0.0481	0.0556
A01DL	Loquats	5	4		0.0120	0.0195	0.0270
A01DP	Pears	5	38		0.0288	0.0399	0.0509
A01DQ	Nashi pears	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01EA	Strawberries	5	60		0.0092	0.0248	0.0403

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01EN	Raspberries and similar-	5	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A01EY	Blueberries	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A01GF	Apricots	5	8		0.1765	0.1784	0.1802
A01GK	Cherries (sweet)	5	14		0.1243	0.1443	0.1643
A01GQ	Plums	5	10		0.0063	0.0198	0.0333
A01HG	Figs	5	7		0.0356	0.0434	0.0513
A01JT	Kiwi fruits (green, red, yellow)	5	15		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01LF	Mangoes	5	4		0.0000	0.0200	0.0400
A01LH	Granate apples	5	29		0.0067	0.0136	0.0204
A01LP	Pineapples	5	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0CGD	Guavas	5	2		0.0995	0.0995	0.0995
A0DTY	Blackberries and similar-	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DVE	Table grapes and similar-	5	57		0.2311	0.2371	0.2431
A0DZB	Oranges	5	62		0.0267	0.0407	0.0547
A01DX	Table grapes	6	57		0.2311	0.2371	0.2431
A01EE	Blackberries	6	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A032F	Sugar and similar, confectionery and water-based sweet desserts	1	26		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A04PA	Sugar and other sweetening ingredients (excluding intensive sweeteners)	2	26		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A033J	Honey	3	26		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03PV	Food products for young population	1	45		0.0000	0.0101	0.0202
A03PY	Infant and follow-on formulae	2	21		0.0000	0.0155	0.0310

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03QX	Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	2	13		0.0000	0.0058	0.0115
A03RC	Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children	2	11		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03QZ	Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	3	13		0.0000	0.0058	0.0115
A03RJ	Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	11		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0EQL	Follow-on formulae	3	8		0.0000	0.0175	0.0350
A0EQM	Infant formulae	3	13		0.0000	0.0142	0.0285
A03PZ	Infant formulae, powder	4	13		0.0000	0.0142	0.0285
A03QK	Follow-on formulae, powder	4	8		0.0000	0.0175	0.0350
A039K	Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	1	20		0.0004	0.0102	0.0200
A03BM	Concentrated or dehydrated fruit/vegetables juices	2	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0BX9	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	2	18		0.0005	0.0086	0.0166
A03BB	Fruit nectars (min. 25-50% fruit as defined in EU legislation)	3	3		0.0000	0.0117	0.0233
A0BY4	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	3	15		0.0006	0.0079	0.0153
A0ETV	Fruit/vegetable juice concentrate	3	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A039T	Juice, cranberry	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03AF	Juice, pineapple	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03AM	Juice, orange	4	13		0.0007	0.0053	0.0099

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03BF	Nectar, mango	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03BG	Nectar, orange	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03BN	Fruit juice concentrates	4	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03CA	Juice concentrate, orange	5	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03LZ	Alcoholic beverages	1	17		0.0000	0.0212	0.0424
A03MS	Wine and wine-like drinks	2	17		0.0000	0.0212	0.0424
A03MT	Wine	3	17		0.0000	0.0212	0.0424
A03MV	Wine, white	4	8		0.0000	0.0225	0.0450
A03MX	Wine, red	4	9		0.0000	0.0200	0.0400
A03KE	Instant coffee (beverage)	4	21		0.0005	0.0011	0.0018
A03KK	Iced coffee	4	12		0.0016	0.0040	0.0063
A03KG	Coffee with milk or cream	4	12		0.0016	0.0040	0.0063
A03KB	Coffee espresso (beverage)	4	15		0.0041	0.0102	0.0163
A03KH	Coffee drink, cappuccino	5	21		0.0016	0.0040	0.0063
A03KA	Coffee beverages	3	35		0.0016	0.0040	0.0063
A03KD	Coffee (weak strength) beverage	4	11		0.0016	0.0040	0.0063
A03KF	Coffee beverage decaffeinated	4	11		0.0016	0.0040	0.0063
A03QF	Infant formula, milk-based, liquid	5	12		0.0000	0.0018	0.0036
A03QR	Follow-on formula, milk-based, liquid	5	12		0.0000	0.0022	0.0044
A03LB	Tea beverages	3	12		0.0004	0.0010	0.0015
A03LG	Herbal and other non-tea infusions	3	12		0.0004	0.0010	0.0015
A03KY	Cocoa beverages	3	22		0.0005	0.0012	0.0019

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset is: Consumption data_CY population.xlsx with 82921 occasions.

Table 3.2: Food consumption survey details

Country	Start Year	End Year	Survey Code	Method of Survey	EU Menu Population	Survey Name	Survey Reference publication
CYPRUS	2014	2018		24h recall	1661	EU-Menu	

3.2.1 Target population

Figure 3.1 shows the number of subjects per population class and categorization between the two genders.

Figure 3.1: Number of subjects in the survey

3.2.2 Weight coefficients to adjust the sample for non – representativeness within the population

Table 3.3: Weight coefficients used

Gender	Population class	Weight coefficient	Number of subjects
FEMALE	Adolescents	265	137
FEMALE	Adults	2,044	139
FEMALE	Elderly	303	129
FEMALE	Infants	32	134
FEMALE	Other children	226	145
FEMALE	Toddlers	66	137
MALE	Adolescents	281	134
MALE	Adults	1,993	134
MALE	Elderly	277	130
MALE	Infants	36	134
MALE	Other children	229	151
MALE	Toddlers	70	137

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Cypermethrin summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Cypermethrin
Substance Category	Pesticide
Reference value	5 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference value	Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Cypermethrin

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0	0	0
Max	2.66	3.088	5.396
Mean	0.099	0.204	0.308
SD	0.145	0.2	0.281
P25	0.016	0.086	0.152
Median	0.051	0.15	0.243
P75	0.122	0.25	0.369
P95	0.34	0.512	0.738
pctOver	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

* pctOver:Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.204 and 0.512 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 5 µg/Kg b.w. per day, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	3.088	0.210	0.197	0.084	0.165	0.264	0.506	0%
MALE	0	2.798	0.197	0.203	0.089	0.138	0.231	0.517	0%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	2.572	0.195	0.194	0.089	0.158	0.219	0.491	0%
Larnaka	0	2.698	0.192	0.206	0.076	0.138	0.229	0.480	0%
Lefkosia	0	2.650	0.196	0.189	0.085	0.145	0.241	0.506	0%
Lemesos	0	3.088	0.229	0.205	0.094	0.167	0.282	0.617	0%
Pafos	0	1.950	0.198	0.206	0.086	0.142	0.231	0.499	0%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.000	1.004	0.174	0.134	0.090	0.135	0.221	0.436	0%
Adults	0.006	1.075	0.166	0.126	0.080	0.137	0.214	0.386	0%
Elderly	0.014	1.226	0.235	0.190	0.101	0.183	0.298	0.628	0%
Infants	0.000	2.698	0.623	0.565	0.253	0.485	0.842	1.947	0%
Other children	0.028	2.002	0.326	0.266	0.159	0.245	0.416	0.819	0%
Toddlers	0.087	3.088	0.664	0.450	0.352	0.526	0.864	1.605	0%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers and infants had 2 or 3 times higher exposure than the other population classes. The lower body weight of these population classes is the main reason for the higher exposure. Also in all population classes the exposure is much lower than the ADI for Cypermethrin intake.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to Cypermethrin by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by Cypermethrin are consumed by all population classes.

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total Cypermethrin exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Apples (11.7%), grapes (9.0%), tomatoes (7.5%), potatoes (5.6%), peaches (5.5%) and cucumbers (4.0%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Cypermethrin intake. In general fruits and some vegetables were the main contributors to the total Cypermethrin exposure. Although, fruits were the most contaminated with Cypermethrin, tomatoes, cucumbers and potatoes, with lower contamination appeared in the main contributors due to their high consumption by the whole population.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Cypermethrin Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Cypermethrin Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	Rice and similar-	1.20%
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal and cereal-like flours	Wheat flour	1.70%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Vegetables and vegetable products	Bulb vegetables	Onions and similar-	Onions	1.14%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Solanacea	Tomatoes and similar-	7.53%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits with edible peel	3.99%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits with inedible peel	3.22%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Spinach-type leaves	Spinaches and similar-	2.17%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Spinach-type leaves	Chards and similar-	2.79%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Legumes with pod	Beans (with pods) and similar-	Slicing bean (young pods)	1.21%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-)	Carrots and similar-	Carrots	1.09%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Herbs and edible flowers	Aromatic herbs	Celery leaves and similar-	1.12%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes	5.59%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Citrus fruits	Oranges and similar-	3.12%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Apples and similar-	11.71%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Pears and similar-	2.39%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Berries and small fruits	Grapes and similar fruits	9.01%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Stone fruits	Cherries and similar-	1.35%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Stone fruits	Peaches and similar-	5.54%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Stone fruits	Apricots and similar-	2.65%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Miscellaneous fruits with edible peel	Figs and similar-	1.15%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	Bananas and similar-	1.15%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	Juice, orange	1.11%
Food products for young population	Infant and follow-on formulae	Follow-on formulae	Follow-on formulae, liquid	1.59%
Food products for young population	Infant and follow-on formulae	Infant formulae	Infant formulae, liquid	1.35%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of Cypermethrin has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to Cypermethrin.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Application of the substitution method on the preparation of occurrence data with high percentage of left-censored data	+
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as Cypermethrin concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an LC-MS/MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.204 and 0.512 µg/kg b.w. per day. It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 5 µg/Kg b.w. per day. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers due to their lower body weight, but also much lower than the ADI.

There was no significant difference in Cypermethrin intake between genders and different geographical areas.

In general fruits and some vegetables were the main contributors to the total Cypermethrin exposure. Apples (11.7%), grapes (9.0%), tomatoes (7.5%), potatoes (5.6%), peaches (5.5%) and cucumbers (4.0%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Cypermethrin intake.

7 References

1. EFSA. 2011b. Evaluation of the FoodEx, the food classification system applied to the development of the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. EFSA Journal 2011; 9(3):1970. [27 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.1970.
2. Peer review of the pesticide risk assessment of the active substance cypermethrin. EFSA Journal 2018;16(8):5402. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5402.
3. Statement on risk mitigation measures on cypermethrin. EFSA Journal 2019;17(10):5822 doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5822.
4. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.
5. EFSA. 2018. Internal report on the harmonisation of dilution factors to be used in the assessment of dietary exposure.

8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices